

MUSEUM ACTIVITIES AND TOURISM IN THE YEARS OF
INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract: *this article shows the changes in the cities of museums and museums in our country and their role in the field of tourism after the exhaustion, and in the development of our country, the interconnectedness of museum cities and tourism is studied. The article also shows the types of museums, their differences from each other. In addition, the article explains the decrees of the President in the field of museums and tourism and their importance. Since 1993, our country has been a member of the International Tourism Organization (UNWTO). Since 2004, the UNWTO office has been operating in Samarkand to coordinate trans-mainline tourism.*

Keywords: *museum, exhibit, tourism, historical, national, monuments, antiquities, archeology, cultural heritage.*

As each state steps towards progress, it is natural to constantly look at its history and strive to study and preserve existing customs, traditions and ancient monuments. And the role of museums in this regard can not be overemphasized. Because they are the sum of the monuments of Culture, Education, nature from the past into a single system and are kept and displayed in accordance with the current traditions.

Since 1977 year in the world traditionally 18 may is celebrated as the International Day of museums. In the years of independence, special attention was paid to the development of museums, which are considered the institutions that preserve our historical heritage. From the very first days of independence, a number of practical works have been carried out on the organization of museums, which include the history of our country and its perennial heritage.

Our country is considered a paradise-land where many saints, scientists and Geniuses were born and lived, and the tourism sector was also developed on a large scale. Although Uzbekistan is relatively new to the tourism sector, it has advanced in many areas of development. Our country has a great potential for the development of international tourism. After gaining independence, our state developed new principles in the field of Tourism. July 27, 1992 Republic of Uzbekistan. The main task of the company is to create a national module of increasing and developing tourism, which was established the National Company "Uzbekturizm" by the decree of the first president of the state policy implementation in the field of Tourism. Since 1993 year, our state is a member of the organization "International Tourism" (UNWTO). Since

2004 (UNWTO) has been operating an office in Samarkand engaged in the management of transcontinental Highway tourism.

The establishment of new museums in our country, the history of the era of the largest and most influential Timurids in the capital, the memory of the victims of the Catastrophe, the opening of the Archaeological Museum in Termez, located in the south of our country, the government has carried out a great deal of work in the field of museum and museum studies. In addition to the establishment of new museums, special attention was paid to the issue of radically improving the activities of all major and minor museums operating up to this time, reorganizing them in the spirit of national independence.

The long three-thousand-year history of the great statehood of our country shows that the Uzbek land has always naturally become the frame of many with its unique economic potential. Over the next one and a half centuries our people lost their overwhelming economic, material, cultural and educational wealth. However, despite these pressures and losses, history also testifies to the fact that the Uzbek people managed to preserve their original identity.

According to the social function of the museum, scientific research and enlightenment (most museums mainly aim at this task, they are also called public museums); research (under the umbrella of scientific research institutes serve as a specific laboratory) and, depending on the educational museums, direction and collections, the network is divided into local (local) and memorial museums. The network will belong to a network of Museums of production, science, art (for example, history museums, Zoological museums). Local museums reflect the history, nature, economy, art, ethnography and other spheres of a particular administrative region. Memorial museums are dedicated to important historical events, outstanding figures [1-30].

Tourism is a new and promising segment of the modern economy. In the latter times, raising the economy of our country to higher levels through the development of tourism in our country has increased to the level of Public Policy. Especially in the great and dark past, a museum under the open sky, which shows our history, is becoming a mass movement to organize trips to historical cities that have become known as cities. In this regard, a number of works are carried out in Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva, which are recognized as "a museum under the open sky".

In 2017-2021, the main tasks for the development of tourism were defined in the state program "year of support for active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies", including the strategy of actions on five priority areas of development of Uzbekistan:

Systematic development of domestic tourism by encouraging local residents to travel around the country, creating a convenient infra-structure for beaches, broad promotion of travel by Regions;

The rapid development of tourism on account of the creation of extensive conditions for the visit of foreign beaches, the enrichment of their travel programs and the expansion of the range of services provided;

The development of tourism as a promising direction of the sphere by forming the appropriate infra structure in the objects of material cultural heritage of our country and the surrounding objects, creating the appropriate conditions for the religious ceremonies to be carried out.

In conclusion, in the years of independence, the activity of museums and tourism grew at a high level, of course, all this was achieved with a lot of effort. The work carried out by the president of our country is of great importance behind these efforts, because they have signed with different countries the mutually beneficial agreements and the Commonwealth of Independent States and opened the path of many opportunities for our people, so I think that we should conduct business with reasonable use of these opportunities.

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